

Carbon Footprint Mitigation Measures in Smart Cities

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Abstract

Based on the eleventh goal of global sustainable development goals concerning smart cities and societies, special attention has to be paid to air quality, climate change reduction, and also waste management in cities. Furthermore, new technologies and management methods can mitigate fossil fuel energy use, reduce air pollution, and minimize global climate change. Suitable collaboration between various components in a smart city with the internet of things and smart city infrastructures like intelligent buildings, the internet, and other physical and technological infrastructures are essential to reach a sustainable smart city that can reduce air pollution, especially carbon dioxide emission. For reducing the carbon footprint in smart cities, using new technologies and government economic, non-economical, and spiritual support to issue mitigating strategies are essential. This study aims to realize the importance of studying the central concept of carbon footprint and its mitigation impact in smart cities and the performance of intelligent components in restraining emission that led to Preventive actions to reduce air pollution in smart cities. Also, the network between all intelligent components, like the economy, citizens, transport, etc., is reviewed to achieve the primary goal.

Keywords: “Sustainable Development Goals,” Carbon footprint,” internet of things,” Climate Change,” “Intelligent Government,” smart city,” carbon dioxide.”

Introduction

The increase in the natural growth rate of the population in the cities, caused by indiscriminate migrations, has faced many challenges in today's cities. Then Moving towards sustainability by reducing greenhouse gases and thus reducing climate change to reach the united nation's vision of 2030 and 2050 is essential by Considering goal 11 of SDGs (sustainable cities and societies), goal number 13 (climate change issues), and goal number 17 (partnership for the goals)[1].

Among the issues related to urbanization and the increase in urban population - the increasing migration of people to cities has resulted in the development of large and small towns and, as a result, destructive and catastrophic effects such as excessive energy consumption, deforestation, extinction of plants and animal species have been on cities. The planet's natural habitats are such a way that cities threaten the earth as the prominent place of human activities and the largest consumer of natural resources[4].

More than 80% of the world's population lives in cities and communities with high-risk pollution and beyond the standards approved by the world health organization (WHO); seven million people worldwide die yearly due to air pollution and related issues[4].

Other crises caused by the increase in population in cities include noise pollution, poverty, traffic, non-participation of citizens in projects leading to sustainability, lack of administrative management, and inability to provide appropriate services. Urbanization and proper urban management are necessary due to the lack of infrastructure that gives cities an uncertain and problematic future[4].

In this way, and according to the issues of industrial and new cities, traditional management methods are no longer responding requirements and needs of today's societies. New solutions must be devised to solve current smart cities' issues[5].

The vital problem of establishing "smart cities" is aligning with the economic, environmental, and social sustainability basis in a systemic and modern perspective and taking care of future generations.

It means creating convenience for citizens by preserving natural and cultural resources and fair distribution of costs, being close to nature, solving traffic problems, improving transportation and communication infrastructures, cultural, social, information, and communication factors and infrastructures, and resource management.

Moreover, energy waste and environmental challenges are changing lifestyles and activities, planning, designing, developing, and modernizing societies.[6]

In addition, a smart city is based on various technologies such as information and communication, electronics, smart transportation, smart building systems, and advanced control structures, and one of the results of this smartening program is helping the environment with less emission of greenhouse gases, mainly carbon dioxide and NOx [7].

To achieve this goal, measurement tools and equipment are used in addition to the Internet, which is one of the necessities of such cities.

In upcoming parts, the results of combining these infrastructures and factors with improving urban performance in reducing emissions will be stated.

Methodology

This research is a cross-sectional descriptive literature review of articles concerning C.F mitigation measures in smart cities. Due to the novelty of both issues of C.F and smart cities and the issue of sustainability, which is one of the essential features for these cities, most studies in this field introduce and then discuss new technology's impact on C.F mitigation.

Following a well-documented guide for developing PRISMA literature review protocols, the critical literature review was conducted in 5 main steps: (I) online database search based on keywords and selection criteria; (ii) refining as per criteria such as language, document type, year, (iii) further refinement based on keywords; (iv) abstract screening; and (v) full-text review.

i. This systematic process is outlined in Figure 1, and the first step involved using the Scopus online database (referencing) to search for literature. Initially, the keywords "smart city" and "carbon footprint" or "CO2 emission" (number of findings 1108).

ii. The second stage of Refining was between 2012-2022. The journal conference or article document type, open access, in the final stage of publication and worldwide in the English language, was used to find articles that were based on "smart city" and "carbon footprint" or "CO2 emission" (number of findings 112).

iii. As we aimed to synthesize the recently published literature, the initial search resulted in 112 articles on smart cities (i.e., using the keywords "mitigation carbon footprint" and "smart cities"). However, only a subset of these articles (i.e., 72) covered both smart cities and these expressions: "carbon footprint, carbon dioxide, air pollution, smart energy."

iv. The 4th step involved screening the abstracts of this subset. Specifically, we reviewed the abstracts for the 72 articles and removed those that did not have actions to mitigate carbon footprint in smart cities as a primary focus. For example, several pieces are in the keyword search in step 2. Still, the authors only discussed carbon footprint and smart cities as potential issues for the work within the abstract rather than the article's primary focus. After the third filter, only 49 articles remained.

v. The final step was a full-text review of the remaining articles. Following the same features as the abstract screening, every 41 pieces were studied in detail. Any not directly focused on smart cities or preventive actions were removed from consideration. This ultimately resulted in 26 peer-reviewed papers that focused primarily on "carbon footprint mitigation actions in smart cities by the intelligent government factor" or "mitigation co2 emissions in smart cities" these articles varied by research category, journal, and year, as discussed below.

Figure (1) Methodology of Research and Refinements.

There were various topical domains and journals within the selected studies. This is due to the diverse nature of the smart city and new technologies that work with IoT introduced recently and in connection with intelligent management, which is the main focus of this research. After that, the classification of the studies based on their related activities and some publication history trends will be discussed. The categorized studies can be filtered due to time, relevance, dates, types of literature review, or other types, including patents and citations, and the nature of preventive action as per its components.

Greenhouse Gas Sources

One of the reasons for the rapid increase in global temperature is the "Enhanced Greenhouse Effect" (that is, the greenhouse effect added to nature due to the release of human-caused greenhouse gases into the atmosphere), which accelerates destructive results such as climate change. Not all greenhouse gases have the same capacity to heat, but their power depends on the radiative forcing they produce and the average time the molecules of that gas stay in the atmosphere.[8]

moreover, the average warming each gas can have is known as the "global warming potential." (GWP) This is calculated mathematically and expressed relative to CO₂. Therefore, the GWP unit is equivalent to carbon dioxide (CO₂-e) [9]. Greenhouse gases (GHGs) warm the Earth by absorbing energy and slowing the rate at which the energy escapes to space; they act like a blanket insulating the Earth. Different GHGs can have different effects on the Earth's warming. There are two key ways these gases differ from each other: their ability to absorb energy (their "Radiative Efficiency") and how long they stay in the atmosphere (also known as their "Lifetime")[9].

The Global Warming Potential (GWP) was developed to allow comparisons of different gas's global warming impacts. It measures how much energy the emissions of 1-ton gas will absorb over a given period or periodic emissions of CO₂.

The larger the GWP, the more given gas warms the Earth compared to CO₂ over the same period. GWPs provide a common standard measure, which allows analysts to add up emissions estimates of different gases (e.g., to compile a national GHG inventor). They will enable policymakers to compare emissions reduction opportunities across sectors and gases. [10].

Carbon Footprint

"The C.F measures the total amount of carbon dioxide emissions that are directly and indirectly caused by an activity or accumulated over a product's life stages." [11]. This definition includes activities of individuals,

populations, governments, companies, organizations, processes, industry sectors, etc. When we talk about products, it has services. All direct (on-site, internal) and indirect emissions (off-site, external, embodied, upstream, downstream) must be considered[12]

The C.F definition can help smart cities research questions for governments and practitioners. CO₂ is a part of greenhouse gases (GHG), but It is essential to consider other substances affecting greenhouse warming too, such as SO_x and NO_x, etc. [11]. However, due to data availability, many are either not carbon-based or more challenging to quantify. Methane can easily be included in this category, but what information can be gained from a partially aggregated index that provides only two of several relevant greenhouse gases? A comprehensive index of greenhouse gases should contain all these gases and is called "climate footprint." As for the "carbon footprint," we choose the most practical and straightforward solution and only include CO₂ [12].

Relation between C.F and Smart Cities

Today, cities and residential areas are much more technologically and digitally transformed. Legacy equipment and facilities are now being upgraded, their performance driven by data analytics. For example, the intelligent network can be integrated with information communication technologies for energy consumption, complex, intelligent control systems for urban traffic control, emergency management, public security systems, and electronic health records for significant medical procedures in hospital management. [13]

Technological changes are the product of many complex social improvements. In the meantime, the need to reduce the climate and environmental footprint, primarily carbon, to provide cleaner energy sources or more efficient services in the field of energy is well recognized because countries are beginning to combat climate changes and closely monitor the impact of climate change on the environment, (for example, the ambitious project of the British government to have net zero emissions by 2050)[14]. Smartening cities can be an ideal solution for creating sustainable and consumption-optimized cultures. Also, C.F reduction, as a part of global climate change mitigation measures, can contribute to sustainability in smart cities, a critical step for smart cities[15].

Discussion

In this research, in addition, to reviewing C.F mitigation measures in smart cities, some studies about the definitions, specifications, and characteristics of C.F and also equipment for measuring CO₂ emissions are red to be able to analyze and further find ways to reduce it. Selected articles are in a period of ten years, from 2012 to 2021. There is also valuable material taken from two related books and reputable sites, such as the United Nations' official website, etc., which will be discussed below. Initially, the characteristics and structure of smart cities have been illustrated. Smart cities have grown and emerged since the beginning of the 21st century. A smart city has several components, including Intelligent infrastructures, Intelligent transportation, Intelligent energies, Intelligent healthcare systems, Intelligent communication systems, Intelligent government, etc. (see Figure 2). These components can create other subcomponents, such as intelligent communication, networks, etc. [6].

Figure (2) Smart City Components.

All of these intelligent components perform with the internet of things (IoT), and each has its role in reducing air pollutants and, consequently, mitigation C.F in smart cities.

Moreover, smart cities are divided into three categories referring to attributes (sustainability, quality of life, urbanization, and smartness), themes (society, economy, environment, governance), and infrastructures (physical, Infrastructure Comprises Physical angels) [6]

According to sustainability studies, one of the most discussed and influential factors is the impact of environmental pollutants on climate change, such as greenhouse gases. The most important part of these air pollutants is C.F and, as studied by [16], is defined as follows in Equation 01:

$$CF = CO_2 + GHG \quad (1)$$

CF= Carbon Footprint, CO₂= Carbon Dioxide, GHG= Green House Gas.

In Conference on Climate Change 2014, the IPCC (International Panel on Climate Change) discussed the issue of C.F in detail, noting that 27 cities with a population of over 10 million worldwide produce about 12.6% of total air pollution in the world. [6]. This shows the importance of examining various methods of reducing C.F in smart and large cities. [17].

It was also stated that proper estimation and analyze the C.F of cities could provide us with more precious information than the basic information of countries' C.F, which is presented in the dimensions of a country and can help policymakers to find better strategies. [16].

Considering the novelty of the SDGs issues raised by the United Nations[1] and the result of the climate change review and considering the assessment of the article "Do smart cities realize their potential to emit less carbon dioxide?", it is concluded that more innovation and creativity have to be used in technologies creating and ways to prevent CO₂ emissions. Of course, it should be kept in mind that each city should act according to its characteristics and climate, infrastructure, limitations, and unique features in providing its solutions, and the answers should be appropriate to the environment of that city and region. [18].

A study conducted in Australia showed that Australia's five biggest smart cities, including Brisbane, Adelaide, Sydney, Melbourne, and Perth alone, emit more than half of the total carbon dioxide produced in Australia. [19].

This study's main results state the importance of C.F mitigation in industrial and smart cities. However, the vital point is the "City Carbon Map" method, and the Life Cycle Approach (LCA) has also been used to estimate all CO₂ emissions. In this way, the C.F in a smart city can be expressed as equation 2 as follows:

$$CF = RTE + EEI + EEE. \quad (2)$$

EEI: emission embodied import (all emissions due to activities in the city's hinterland resulting from globalization).

EEE: emission embodied export (all products and services exported from cities, leading to emissions).

RTE: Remaining Territorial Emission (all emissions inside the territory of a city).

This study has shown that the most critical and challenging cause of CO₂ emissions in these smart cities is energy consumption for electricity generation. Then more attention should be paid to using new renewable energies to replace fossil fuels. Also, the government supports the launch and use of helpful software such as "Climate Change Tracker" to identify areas with high potential emissions and then ratify policies to reduce carbon emissions there [19].

Another study is concerned with reviewing actions to mitigate C.F in smart cities by utilizing new technologies connected to the internet. They are considered part of IoT in smart cities to manage and optimize energy consumption and enlarge the efficiency of infrastructure, transport, healthcare, or other services. As a practical implementation, Figure 3 shows how big data collected in a smart city can produce helpful information for an intelligent government to make wise decisions or issue innovative policies [20].

Figure (3) Framework Using Ensemble Regression Model [4].

Also, following these innovations, one of the new issues raised in utilizing traffic information in the urban management system is a model of an intelligent approach to identify areas with a high volume of pollutant emissions. This system performs with the capability to monitor and manage traffic lights and management. All places with more traffic jams are considered to be high potential CO₂ emission zone and, then, it guides traffic on the other roads and tries to vanish traffic density at a remarkable point and then try to reduce transport time for vehicles in the city by controlling traffic; this system can work efficiently in heavy traffic areas and smart cities, consequently reducing C.F. [4]

Figure 4 shows the interrelation between controlling traffic density in a smart city and sustainability.

Figure (4) Intelligent Traffic and Carbon Footprint Mitigation.

Another study conducted in Europe and funded by the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) was “Optimising the energy Use in cities with a smart decision support system (OPTIMUS).” This framework is a web-based tool that uses the internet and implements the SCEAF (Smart City Energy Assessment Framework) sub-Framework and provides the energy managers with a platform for assessing the performance of the city as a whole or city’s each building in terms of energy optimization, CO₂ emissions reduction and energy cost minimization[21]

In studying the energy consumption of smart cities, the Smart City Energy Performance (SCEP) can be evaluated as the performance of the city amount on each of the three-axis (Political Field of Action (PFA), Environmental & Energy Profiles (EEP), and Related Infrastructures & ICT (information and communication technology) (I&I) and as retrieved from [18] as follows Equation 3:

$$SCEP (PFA, EEP, RI \& I) = (W_{pfa} * PFA) + (W_{eep} * EEP) + (W_{ri\&i} * RI\&I) \quad (3)$$

The added value of the proposed methodology lies in the combination of energy efficiency and management using multidisciplinary data sources. The proposed framework can be applied to different types of buildings, such as municipal and office buildings, entertainment or sports facilities, etc., and was used in some notable buildings like A) Savona, “Colombo-Pertini School,” in Italy (6.092 m²), B) Sant Cugat, “Sant Cugat Town Hall,” in Spain (8.593 m²). C) Sant Cugat, “Sant Cugat Theatre”, in Spain (4.150 m²). D) Zaanstad, “Zaanstad Town Hall,” in the Netherlands (18.531 m²), all those with significant buildings and spaces that can show the effort of this model better. [21]

The potential impact of the action plan for scheduling the set point temperature is estimated at a 5-10% reduction of the energy consumption for cooling/heating. Indeed, there is a 5% to 6% reduction in total HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) energy consumption for each rise in supply-air temperature setpoint, depending on climate. In addition, a decrease of 1 K in internal temperature will reduce energy consumption by 6%.

The targeted energy plans of the ‘Optimization’ pillar derive from the DSS (decision support system) for the energy management component, which offers short-term actions every week, and from the DSS for Energy Efficiency measures feature, which offers long-term efforts every year. [18].

In research that was done by supporting the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) and a grant funded by the Korean government in 2016 about the Analysis of Intelligent transportation systems for a sustainable environment in smart Cities, the role of transportation administrators in mitigating climate change is identified by preventing carbon emissions caused with reducing traffic density in smart cities. In recent works on the Internet of Vehicles (IoV), “intelligence” and “sustainability” have been the keywords in the context of transportation. The term “transportation system” has been reformed to “Intelligent Transportation System” (ITS) owing to rapid developments and advancements in recent transportation technologies [4]

The main objectives of the IoV are the collection or sharing of information about the vehicle, road infrastructure, or vehicle user and the processing of this information to guide or supervise vehicles efficiently to prevent accidents and road traffic congestion and thereby make the driving experience safe and enjoyable for the drivers/passengers. Despite the advancements in vehicular transportation, maintaining transportation sustainability is an essential and challenging task. Transport sustainability involves managing go-green transportation and establishing effective transportation planning systems to ensure road traffic safety. Managing transportation sustainability led to mitigating environmental carbon emissions and preventing climate change, a primary mission of governments worldwide [4]

That study suggests the development of an autonomous intelligent or autonomous smart car that incorporates all managing methodologies by using IoT, along with weather- and road-surface-assistance technologies, and achieves sustainability characteristics. The accident data analysis report based on weather and road surface conditions would aid in taking necessary precautionary measures to prevent vehicle collisions. Autonomous vehicles are expected to be the next-generation vehicles in the transportation sector; hence, more intelligent utilization of autonomous vehicles in various ways, such as autonomous taxis, will enhance transportation and make it brighter. Realizing this futuristic suggestion will require considerable effort; however, developing such futuristic technology will pave the way for more straightforward, more intel, safer, and more sustainable transportation [22].

Lighting is responsible for 19% of the global use of electrical energy and accounts for about 6% of the total emissions of greenhouse gases. [23] One of the actions that can reduce climate change due to carbon emission mitigation is using fewer resources caused by managing lightening cities and buildings, which can be done in smart cities using IoT. The IPSO (guidelines defined by the internet protocol (IP) for Smart Objects Alliance (IPSO Alliance) application can provide an intelligent framework to control lighting in smart cities with criteria like Chronological and astronomical scheduling, Environmental and human behavior, Concrete Events programming, Alarm conditions, and Complex Program Logic or Intelligent Inference. The integration of intelligent control on a lighting management system also contributes to a sustainable architecture and lighting systems designs such as green energy environments where through intelligent control interfaces, it is possible to remotely monitor and operate the whole system to achieve an efficient operating mode at the same time that preserving an appropriate behavior depending on the physical world interactions with the system alongside reducing energy consumption and reduce costs. This research presented the relevance of intelligent lighting control to reach the sustainability of smart cities that caused mitigating climate change. This has described the impact on the total power consumption of the lighting and, consequently, the interest in offering a higher control [23].

According to another study conducted at the polytechnic university of Madrid in Spain (UPM) [24], the amount of CO₂ emissions by attendance, including working people, students, visitors, etc., can be a good indicator of the level of government performance in CO₂ emission control. In this study, the carbon emitted by commuters to mentioned university is estimated and categorized by commuters’ characteristics, including groups, campus, ages, and even genders. Furthermore, find out that only 16% of computers used private cars are responsible for over half the daily trip’s CO₂ emissions. Then, in this case, municipal and UPM authorities can take preventive actions in accordance to the intelligent management and using other intelligent components by establishing incentive, punitive and cultural policies like providing better public transport accessibility to campuses, improving the public transport infrastructure for all campuses even in unsuitable locations, providing higher frequencies and a better connection with other

modes, purchase of smaller and more efficient vehicles like electric cars, increasing of charging infrastructure for transport electrification, the promotion of shared mobility, parking management strategies, environmental education, and online teaching strategies [24].

On the other hand, regarding the IoT's role in smart cities and the impact of using technological resources that an intelligent government may support, it has been determined that intelligence has to start from human life's most essential details, like utilizing intelligent devices in homes. According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency report in 2020 Electricity Manufacturing is caused for 28% of commercial and & Housing 12 % of C.F in the world.[25]

Even though all five of these contributors are essential for the livelihoods of millions, there is still hope to minimize by finding effective ways to utilize and supply electricity. It is stated that in houses with an IoT system with sensors to maintain the home temperature at the optimum level, 22.4% less carbon is produced in regulating the temperature procedures of the house than in houses without this system [26].

Installing such sensors involves cost and culture too, which is led by that society's age, social class, education, and culture. Then intelligent governments have a significant role in implementing those culture buildings and the challenge of establishing these sensors[13].

By creating an intelligent system consisting of car sensors and databases and then connecting these systems to simple software in drivers' smartphones, accurate information in the field of CO₂ emissions can be provided to urban management agents for further action. It has been piloted in Thailand and Bangkok, and its name is low power vast area network (LPWAN). It can be used to create a unified database to control and manage C.F emissions. Intelligent transport can collaborate with intelligent management to reduce C.F. [27].

The role of creating a database and an intelligent system to identify places with high C.F was examined in a project carried out in collaboration with the Unitec Institute of Technology and the national institute of water and atmospheric research (NIWA) in New Zealand and taken in the city of Rangiora; it shows the collaboration of intelligent government with intelligent citizens to monitor air quality can lead preventing to enter a risky air quality area and it can be a good move toward mitigating C.F in smart cities[28]. The process of this system, named "Airtify," is shown in Figure 5.

Figure (5) Processing Chain of Airtify Network.[28]

This information can be provided to consumers online, using relevant software on the citizen's smartphone with fixed sensors placed at locations exposed to a representative particulate matter concentration of the surroundings. Moreover, by creating an ethical culture, these consumers prevent further emissions. [28]

Another survey about optimization tools for energy efficiency management of street lighting systems in smart cities was carried out in Bari (southern Italy). Unfortunately, street lighting energy supply is a cause of excessive CO₂ emissions by the public administration and using sensors to optimize their working hours significantly reduces C.F[29]. This study argues that Combining intelligent government with intelligent energy can serve a critical role in setting a sustainable smart city by issuing appropriate policies and decisions in time[30].

In another study conducted by the University of South Florida and the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, the performance collaboration of intelligent transport with the intelligent government was surveyed. [31]

It introduced a new way of collecting data using wireless sensor networks (WSNs) consisting of small, efficient, low prices autonomous nodes to monitor from the stationary nodes deployed in the city. Figure7 shows the Structure of Wireless Sensor Networks: A) Communication Part, B) Memory Region, and C) Sensor Node, retrieved from, shows how a WSN system works.

Figure (6) How is WSN Working?[31]

it is a concept with the inclusion of the IoT and long-term evolution mobile (LTE-M) modules that are low-cost, efficient systems for machine-to-machine (M2M) devices. It can monitor air pollution in all parts of a smart city by using stationary and mobile nodes and transfer data to the big clouds to analyze the air pollution concept and then set a suitable policy to reduce C.F [31].

In one study that was supported and promoted by the National Social Science Fund of China High-Level Talent Project of Hainan Natural Science Foundation; and the Research Start-up Fund of Hainan University in 231 cities in china about the effect of smart city construction on emission reduction and the impact of smart city construction on energy-saving and relation between Energy efficiency as a mechanism for the construction of the smart city to reduce emissions, showing that smart city construction has significantly reduced per capita CO₂ emissions, with a reduction effect of approximately 18.42 logarithmic percentage points and also The impact of smart city construction on C.F reduction is more evident in cities with higher administrative levels, higher levels of neutral technological progress and green innovation, and higher levels of advanced industrial structure and smart city construction achieves energy savings and reduces per capita CO₂ emissions by improving energy efficiency. [32]. It can be defined as a linear relation of intelligent government with the intelligent economy in smart cities. This means that smart cities with higher levels of economic smartness often have a higher level of technological progress and green innovations.

These actions were made by the Chinese government within ten years from 2011 to 2021 and then evaluated in mentioned study. It can be referred to as the contribution of intelligent government to intelligent buildings and infrastructures [32]. After a detailed case study in china, the result argued that emission reduction should be based on energy-saving goals. The mediation effect indicates that most of the carbon emission reduction effects of smart city construction are caused by energy conservation, accounting for 63% of the total development. Therefore, the intelligent government assumes the need to pay attention to the smartening cities and then Strengthen the “green” orientation of smart city construction. [32].

In another study, the “Smart Energy Regions” in Europe, building standards towards the ZEB concept (energy buildings), which is an integral part of smart cities, and the role of zero energy buildings in intelligent energy regions were evaluated. Intelligent governments issue these policies to reduce energy consumption in smart buildings and mitigate C.F [33]. Zero energy buildings (ZEBs) are described as buildings with zero carbon emissions annually and are concerned with Environmental design, building practices, Renewable Energy Sources, labeling of technical building systems, and Intelligent Energy Management in smart cities. ZEBs will contribute significantly to smart cities in the energy efficiency, conservation, and renewable energy generation aspects.

According to this study, an intelligent government needs intelligent buildings in smart cities to save energy. Then less GHG emissions using current and corresponding regulations like zero energy standards in European countries or the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan that activities have commenced since 2010 and are realized through the European Industrial Initiatives and as follows:

- Wind Initiative
- Solar Europe Initiative – photovoltaic and concentrated solar power.
- Electricity Grid Initiative.
- Carbon Capture, Transport, and Storage Initiative.
- Sustainable Nuclear Initiative.
- Industrial Bioenergy Initiative.
- Smart Cities & Communities Initiative.
- Joint Technology Initiative on fuel cells and hydrogen.

Furthermore, its provision includes buildings, Heating and Cooling, Electricity, Transport, Advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), and Smart grids. This plan and regulations can move forward in reducing climate change to 2030 and then 2050 visions and can numerate as a preventive action in smart cities. [33]

Conclusion

In the new era of modernization and alongside Improvement Technologies in many aspects of human life, smart cities need to have excellent and optimum strategies to achieve SDGs by producing and managing energy resources. Paying attention to reducing air pollutants with the partnership of all smart city components on a suitable path toward sustainability to minimize climate change is essential in smart cities.

One of the leading prominent roles of intelligent government is to set a suitable energy management system to reduce air pollution, C.F, and climate change (as shown in Figure 7).

Figure (7) Collaboration of Smart City Components to Mitigate Climate Change.

Furthermore, an intelligent government cannot perform well alone and needs partnerships with other smart city components.

Reducing climate change in smart cities can be done with effort, perseverance, and targeted management decisions. This process reflects the innovative decision-making process and the impact of intelligent government, which leads to the establishment of policies for air pollution monitoring and measurement of environmental pollutants and C.F, and these monitoring provide appropriate information to the intelligent governments to adopt policies to prevent air pollution and carbon emissions, which will ultimately reduce climate change.

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